

The Lack of Hope Among the Japanese Youth

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Abstract

In Japan, the diminishing hope among the youth has been a topic of discussion. The youth is both the driving force behind innovation and productivity, which makes this issue alarming. Consequences can be lack of work motivation, low birth rate, and losing precious human resources. The study aims to explore the alarming trend of the disenchantment of the youth in Japan by providing a literature review and analysis using data such as the Nippon Foundation's 2024 62nd Survey on Attitudes Toward Country and Society (Six-Country Study: Japan, the United States, the United Kingdom, China, South Korea, and India) of 1,000 adolescents ranging from 17 to 19 years of age. By comparing datasets with other nations, the study places the concern in a broader context and highlights the seriousness of the lack of hope among the youth in Japan. Overall, the perception that one cannot influence their country, economic uncertainties, traditional values that resist change and hinder technological advancement, and the impact of the aging population that is seen as a financial burden are several factors contributing to the problem. This study contributes to current literature by highlighting the relationship between the lack of Japanese youths' optimism and hope for Japan.

Introduction

Hope and optimism are crucial factors in determining the future of a nation (Graham, 2024). For Japan, a country renowned for its technological advancements, the lack of hope among the youth is a concerning problem and presents a significant challenge as it can hinder Japan's economic and global growth. The youth of a country represent the driving force behind innovation and societal change, making this lack of hope a much more alarming concern ((Nippon Foundation, (2024), Page 7)). Why should anyone care about the lack of hope among the younger generation? If the future generation were to be devoid of hope, they would find no means to contribute to society in terms of motivation for work or giving birth. Also, elite prospects would soon start to fly out of Japan, resulting in a loss of productivity and global standing for Japan. Although Japan is praised for its high quality of life due to its extensive support from the government and efficient services, the situation might not be the same after its downfall. Following the downfall, the country might face economic downturns coupled with a shrinking workforce, challenging its ability to maintain social security and healthcare services at their current levels. By conducting a thorough literature review of credible sources, the

study aimed to uncover the factors underlying the lack of hope among the youth. Additionally, comparing the state of Japan with other nations, such as the US and UK, allows the readers to view the issue in a much more global context. The research fills in several gaps in the existing literature. First, it establishes a correlation between the perceived lack of power to influence a nation and hope for the nation. Second, it dives deeper into the economic uncertainties and traditional values associated with the problem. Third, it addresses the role of the aging population in Japan and demographics on the issue.

Methods

Objective and Scope

This study is a literature review that incorporates survey data and analysis from existing research to explore why Japanese youth lack hope for their country. A survey presented by the Nippon Foundation, '62nd Survey on Attitudes Toward Country and Society (Six-Country Study: Japan, the United States, the United Kingdom, China, South Korea, and India), of 1,000 adolescents ranging from 17 to 19 years of age, was examined to determine the problem of the lack of hope among the Japanese youth. This comparison helps contextualize the attitudes of Japanese youth in a global framework, helping to highlight the problem.

Search Strategy

Studies found on platforms such as Google Scholars and data from organizations, for example, the 'Ministry of Health, Labour, and Welfare', were selected. The study overall focused on government reports and credible industry publications such as McKinsey and the Ministry of Health, Labour, and Welfare, spanning from 2000 to 2024. Furthermore, these studies were limited to the English and Japanese languages.

Keywords: Japanese Youth, voter participation, lack of hope

Data analysis

Quantitative research was conducted by acquiring data sets from previous studies and government reports. Graphs were used to analyze voter growth estimates to support the identification of factors contributing to youth disenchantment. For instance, the 2019 Nippon Foundation survey titled *18-Year-Old Attitude Survey*, which was conducted in India, Indonesia, South Korea, Vietnam, China, the United Kingdom, the United States, Germany, and Japan, was utilized to compare the sections on lack of hope and confidence in changing one's nation. Additional analyses included charting Japan's

pension data to explore correlations with findings from the 2019 survey. Charts and graphs were generated using P5 editor coding software.

Results

1. Hope and power

A correlation was based on the lack of hope amongst the youth and the belief that they don't hold power to change their nation by observing the 2019 Nippon Foundation survey titled *18-Year-Old Attitude Survey, targeted towards nine nations: Japan, United States, UK, India, Indonesia, Vietnam, Korea, and China*. The percentage of individuals who believed they could change their nation by their own efforts among those who answered that their nation was going to either get better or worse was investigated.

Note: China was excluded since there was only one sample for “nation becomes worse.”

The answer options for “not change” and “not sure” were removed.

The graph shows a positive correlation between how hopeful a person feels for their nation and their belief in the ability to change it through their efforts. For Japan, 37.5% of the 96 individuals who answered positively for hope for their nation believed they were capable of influencing it. In contrast, only 17.9% of the 379 individuals who expressed a lack of hope for their nation believed they were capable of making an

impact. Similarly, in the United States, while 77.9% of the hopeful 302 citizens believed in their ability to shape their country, a mere 58.8% of the 296 individuals who were less hopeful shared this belief (Nippon Foundation, 2019, Page 5). In all six nations studied, the more they felt capable of influencing their country, the more hopeful they were. Thus, the perception of not being able to change one's nation is a contributing factor to the lack of hope in Japan.

1.1 Excessive power among the old generation

So why do the Japanese youth feel powerless? Japan is infamous for its aging society and policies that heavily favor the older generation. The average age of Japanese politicians was 62.4 years old, placing the country first globally, with Korea following closely at 0.6 years younger (Honkawa, 2022, Page 1). This demographic trend, combined with an aging society, has created a downward spiral where politicians prioritize the interests of the elderly to secure electoral success (REGALADO et al., 2021).

In response to these concerns, recent efforts to increase voter turnout among the younger generation have been made. For example, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communication granted 18 and 19-year-olds the opportunity to vote in 2016 to centralize politics for the youth, and strategies such as featuring celebrities popular with younger audiences in awareness campaigns and creating educational videos were taken. Additionally, commission staff have reached out to high schools, where they offer on-site classes that explain the basics of voting and advance voting processes ("Low Youth Voter Turnout Casts Shadow Over Tokyo Gubernatorial Poll," 2024). Other methods were partnerships with companies such as Uber Eats and Luup, a growing electrical keyboard company in Japan. Despite some progress, the gap in voter turnout rates between different age groups still exists. According to the Tokyo Election Administration Commission's statistics for the last gubernatorial election four years ago, the average turnout rate for those aged 20 to 39 grew by 11.6% compared to 2014, recording a rate of 45.296%. Still, the numbers are insignificant compared to the turnout rates for those aged 40 and older, as the rate was 59.621%, a 7.2% increase from

2014.

However, the disproportionate influence of older generations in Japan's political landscape is not solely due to the lack of youth voters; it is an inevitable consequence of the nation's demographic features (Fujiwara, 2021, 35). The graph above illustrates the demographic features of Japan in 2023: 16% of the population is between the ages of 0 and 19, 20.4% of the population is between 20 and 39, and the remaining 63.6% is taken by people 40 or older. In other words, this distribution grants the elderly a substantial influence on election outcomes. Even if 100% of the eligible voters between 20 and 39 vote, it only takes approximately 32% of people older than 40, otherwise regarded as elderly, to wipe out the effect of young voters. Meanwhile, in nations such as the U.S., 26.8% of the population is aged between 20 and 39, and 48.6% is older than 40; therefore, nearly 55% of the elderly are required to invalidate the youths statements. Under democracy, a majority vote is the optimal option for deciding to establish the national agenda and is highly beneficial for the elderly in Japan, where they make up a majority of the population.

2. Uncertainties towards the Nation

For the past 30 years, Japan's economy has stagnated, resulting in the era known as the 'lost 30 years' (Iwasaki, 2020). As a financial burden pressures the younger generation regarding expenses such as the consumption tax rising by 2% in 2019 and health insurance premiums growing steadily, the average salary has barely changed. According to the Statistics Bureau of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, the average salary per worker grew only from 4.4 million yen in 1990 to 4.6 million yen in 2023. Furthermore, the financial burden has been amplified by the value of the yen dropping, which adds to the economic strain by making international

travel more costly.

According to the IMD (Institute for Management Development), Japan was ranked 11th in terms of competitiveness in 2003 but then fell to 38th in 2024. In addition, GDP per capita dropped to 38th in 2022. From this, it can be said that the lack of global competitiveness is the key reason for Japan's economic stagnation. The graph below shows the breakdown for Japan's World Competitiveness Ranking. As shown, business efficiency is the key element to the downfall of Japan, falling from 19th in 2014 to 55th in 2020. A breakdown of "business efficiency" shows that "productivity and efficiency" and "attitudes and values" (e.g., digitalization readiness, adaptability to change) are especially low for Japan, making them the key factors in the country's diminishing competitiveness (Makita, 2022, Page 8).

**Figure 8. IMD World Competitiveness Ranking
<Breakdown for Japan>**

Source: Prepared by JRI based on IMD, "World Competitiveness Ranking"

2.1 Low productivity

Given Japan's declining population, the economy ought to be more productive than ever; however, Japan's productivity and efficiency remain low. Research conducted by McKinsey indicates the low productivity of several sectors and that a lack of competition is a contributing factor to these economic challenges. The study measured the

productivity of residential construction, retailing, food processing, and health care sectors and compared it with that in benchmark countries (e.g., the US and France). Then they analyzed the cause of the productivity gap between Japan and the benchmark country at the production process level (i.e., what managers are doing differently). The comparison of the productivity of the four sectors in the US (set at 100%) was as follows: 35% for food processing, 50% for retailing, 45% for residential construction, and 93% for health care. While Japan excels in manufacturing with a productivity rate of 120%, this strength is not mirrored in the other sectors. For the retail sector, small mom-and-pop shops accounted for 55% of retail employment in Japan, while the numbers are 19% in the US and 26% in France. These small businesses struggle with weak merchandise since they lack the scale to invest in new technology. In the food processing sector, despite having six times more food processing establishments per capita than the US, each of them only produced one tenth of the value of the US counterpart. Despite this, in Japan, government funding has kept indebted and uncompetitive divisions of large conglomerates afloat, which hinders economic advancement. In addition, Japan has barriers that prevent new competitors from entering certain sectors, resulting in a lack of domestic competition (Aoki et al., 2000, Page 40).

2.2 Attitudes and values

The traditional ideal of committing to a company until retirement, rather than seeking new opportunities to obtain new skills, has limited career mobility for workers (Nocos et al., 2023). This is reinforced by the age-based promotion system, which rewards long tenure with better treatment rather than performance-based results. Furthermore, Japan is infamous for its unpaid overtime work, which values quantity over quality. According to the 'Monthly Labor Survey Results for 2022', by the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare, the average overtime total per month for a worker was 13.8 hours. Although the numbers have been declining recently, the belief still exists.

Japan slid to a new low in an annual digital competitiveness ranking released in 2023, underscoring the Japanese nation's struggle to adopt new technology and fund technological advances. The ranking was based on government data and survey responses from business executives, determined by three factors: knowledge, technology, and future readiness. Japan fell to 32nd place out of 64 economies compared to when the data was taken in 2017. This was evident during the pandemic when the nation gathered patient information using fax. Explanations for this can be a lack of skilled digital workers or aging executives of companies (*What Is a Digital Lagging Country? Japan's Position in the Digital Competitiveness Rankings.*, 2024).

It is not a novel idea that, when facing the declining population in Japan, it is essential to have an efficient digital industry. Nevertheless by 2030, Japan is projected to lack 790,000 IT engineers. In response, the Kishida administration has promised to create 2.3 million IT workers by the end of 2026 (Kobayashi, 2023). However, Japanese companies' adherence to traditional ways, such as communicating through fax, may hinder growth (Loh, 2021). The reluctance to embrace change and implement new technology might impede Japan's digital development.

2.3 Aging Population

The current economic conditions in Japan have depressed wages, and despite several policy changes, the younger population thus does not have enough confidence to begin starting families. This has resulted in a gradual shrinkage of the population. On the other hand, personal wealth has, naturally, grown over time, along with the extended life expectancy due to the latest medical technologies (Edmond & North, 2023). This has not only led to a huge hole in the workforce but has also set a seemingly insuperable financial burden on the younger generation.

Data acquired from the Japan Pension Service.

The graph above shows the number of recipients receiving elderly pensions from the nation and the average monthly amount for each individual, spanning from 2010 to 2022. As the line graph shows, while the amount each month has stayed relatively the same this decade, the number of recipients has increased almost by 8 million. The Ministry of Health, Labour, and Welfare states that by the end of 2050, a single worker will have to support 0.83 people, which is shocking compared to 1960, when a single worker only had to support 0.09 people financially. This is truly disturbing for the youth and certainly diminishes hope.

Limitations

The study was limited to papers and datasets that were freely accessible online, potentially restricting the variety of sources reviewed. However, credible data, such as

2024 data from the Nippon Foundation, known for its trustworthiness, was used to mitigate the lack of sources. Additionally, while the qualitative data provide valuable context, not all of them are up-to-date and may not fully reflect the most current developments. Yet, the data used were regarding population growth and productive level for Japan, which follow a relatively similar pattern to the past, thus not affecting the quality of the data by a large amount.

Recommendation for future research

Conducting a more longitudinal study of the youth's engagement with society and their hopes can benefit the field by providing valuable insights on changes in policies and measures that might have affected the youth.

Collecting more data can strengthen the fact that the perception of not being able to change one's nation is a contributing factor to the lack of hope in Japan.

Expanding the comparative analysis to include more nations with the same kind of demographic as Japan can test if the phenomenon of lack of hope is a similar concern for those nations.

Collecting the latest data that directly states why the youth lack hope can highlight the factors contributing to the problem currently. These can be policies or beliefs that underlie everyday life.

Discussion

This study aimed to understand the components contributing to the lack of hope among the youth in Japan. The findings of the study reveal that the perception of the Japanese youth not being able to change one's nation is affecting their sense of hope towards their nation. In addition, Japan's economic uncertainties, traditional values among the executives of companies, weak digital power, and aging population are also likely to affect the level of hope. These findings indicate that for the younger generation to possess hope towards a country, nations must implement policies where the youth can hold power to affect a nation regardless of the nation's demographics. Traditional ways are fair in terms of majority votes but can grant far greater power to countries where their demographics are shifted to the older generation. This can be seen in countries like Japan, where the elderly population greatly surpasses the youth. Also, a country's economic state and attitudes towards change can alter the level of hope. Focusing on the economic state, it is essential that the youth are not burdened by the financial concerns, that domestic competition is robust for a productive economy, and that companies are adaptable to change. One important contribution of this paper is discovering the connection between youth power and hope for a nation.

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